

Self Employment Opportunities and Challenges

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.14936518

Abstract:

At some point of employee they feel the desire to be self-employed. Being your own boss sounds really tempting. But, if this is the only reason behind your wish to be self-employed, then, let need to think twice before deciding to proceed on a self-employed career path. Not everyone gets the chance to taste success by starting their own business. You need to have a crystal clear vision of what you want to do and your final goals. Self-employment gives you space to earn limitless but then again, you need to work really hard to achieve your goals.

Employment Opportunities for Men:

Business Venture: Starting your own business is one of the great ideas; unfortunately it is also one which requires not only capital but a lot of hard work and patience from you side. Anything that you are interested in or are good at, can be turned into a business venture. If you are good at cooking, start a catering business, if you are good at marketing, take up an agency or a franchise for a big company, if you are good at advertising, you can start-up an advertising firm. Before setting up this business, however, business plans and business capital should be in place. You should also be aware of your competition, the amount of business loan required and the ability to see yourself through the first few tough months. The key here is to be realistic and make realistic goals rather than getting emotional and carried away.

Small Business from Home: If you feel that you do not have the required amount of skills and/or capital, there are plenty of small business opportunities that you can start from your home. You could start being an event planner for parties. Do not

assume that being an event planner is the job of a woman. No sir, you can also be an event planner. Start with small events and with the help of a small group of people who are either struggling to get noticed or are ready to help you out without any expectations in return. With one success following the other, in no time you can start expanding your business as well as your staff. Finally, you can move out from the house and have your own office. Event management is not cakewalk; on the bright side it is one of the self employment ideas with a low start, and hence you need not worry about the start-up capital.

Cleaning Services: Hire a few people to work for you, buy or rent the equipment that you need and start off a cleaning service company. You can start off in your neighborhood and if the feedback is good, great, start advertising and expand your business. You could either start with cleaning the whole house, or you could just clean the pools.

Internet Jobs: On line jobs are available in plenty. Starting off with an online job is

one to the quick self employment ideas. If you do not want to do a job, you can start off your own website or you can start making websites for other vendors. This does not require a lot of capital investment. If making websites is not your forte, then you can start off with online marketing. On line marketing is one of the various work at home ideas, which, again, does not require a lot of capital investment from your side.

Work From Home Jobs:

Data Entry: One of the easiest jobs, data entry can be done by sitting at home. If you are a stay at home dad, data entry jobs can be handled along with the various responsibilities around the house. This does not require you to work for a fixed duration everyday nor does it require any sort of capital investment.

Car Wash: Car wash is so costly, nowadays. Start your own car wash service, where you provide the car wash at reasonable prices. Don't worry, if you can show people that you give a great service, your customers will increase ten fold.

Consultancy: You are an expert on so many different subjects. So, why not start a consultancy at home, where in you can provide your customers with the satisfactory answers to their problems. Your knowledge and your education will be put to good use if you start business consultant in your own consultancy.

Real Estate: If you are good at marketing and are good with people, why not use your skills to earn some great money. A realtor's job can be started easily without the help of any other people. With your contacts and your skills, rock the real estate world.

Interior Designer: If you have the knowledge of making good use of space utilization and if you can decorate a room with a very pleasing effect, this is the career for you. Start with a friend's house and see your dream come true.

Employment Opportunities for Women:

A woman might not always work. This is especially true of various cultures across the globe and not necessarily just USA. Apart from the limitations of receiving less education or other family restrictions, every woman either takes a break or puts her career development on hold when she comes in the family way. At such a time (or even others) self employment is a great option to look into. This article will help by giving some self employment ideas for women.

Women's Self Employment Ideas: Self employment for anyone is a great idea. For one, it makes you self sufficient and prevents you from depending on anyone for work, and even if you're not working professionally, it still provides financial stability and instills in one a feeling of independence. Here are some self employment ideas that you can work with.

Home Business: Starting a business is not really that much of a hassle, especially for a small business. Yes, it can take some time to develop contacts and a customer base, but if the product or service that you're selling is good, then it won't take long for word to flow and a successful business to be made. A work at home business could be anything from making purses, a home based boutique, selling cosmetics, starting a beauty salon, preparing and selling food items and the like. Start out on a small scale and then let

the business grow according to demands, time and finances.

Tutoring and Teaching: Extra help at studies is always essential for school going or college kids, but unfortunately, parents may not have the time or related expertise in taking up this task. This is where you come in. Spread the word around that you can help make their math base strong or improve their communication skills. Even simply guiding them through their homework everyday and recording their progress will go a long way in shaping their studies and making them responsible and better students.

Hobby Classes: This idea is bound to be successful in the summers when children have a lot of free time. Start hobby classes like painting, cooking, drawing, singing, musical instruments, stitching etc and plan a week-long schedule (or whatever suits you best) to teach them this. This is a great idea for work at home moms. You can have various batches of these all year through as well.

Photography: Just pick up a camera and choose a field that you like, then start shooting. Sell these pictures to ad agencies, photo agencies and the like. There are many women who specialize in a particular area of photography -for example, newborns, functions etc. Once the word spreads around, then people who don't want to have extravagant functions or are looking for a personal touch in their photos, will contact you for the same. Make sure that you learn a few marketing strategies like distributing pamphlets or word of mouth publicity or giving an ad in the newspaper. So that the word spreads.

Start a Website: Starting a website is one of the best methods to make money

online. If you have HTML knowledge and the like then starting one will be no problem. If a website seems like too much work then blogging, video blogging or writing articles for sites, commenting on author pages, and similar such online jobs will also help one earn money.

Child Care Center: If you have the available space then there is really nothing like starting a day care or child care center. Of course, you need to be patient with kids and be able to handle them and love to be around them. A degree in psychology really helps for this work at home job and pays great as well.

Advantages of Self Employment:

- Self-employment gives you the freedom to do what you love to do. You are free to choose whom you want to work with and whom not.
- You can make your own decisions about your work and there will be no one to question your decisions.
- Job Insecurity cannot hit you. You are your own boss and you cannot get fired. So you have total control over your career and job.
- If you want to go for a vacation, then you no longer need to take permission from anyone. There is no limited number of leaves or a specific vacation time. Just you have to arrange your work perfectly, so that it gets completed according to your time.
- You can have great benefits if you work hard and in a right way.
- Being your own boss is itself a great feeling and boosts your confidence and potential.
- You can work whenever you want to and choose your own work place and conditions.

- Unlike other forms of employment, there is no need for a self employed person to miss special occasion due to work. It's upon you how you manage your timings. So, self-employment helps to maintain a perfect decorum between work, family and friends.
- Self-employment gives you an opportunity to show your others skills you have regardless of your qualification degree.

Disadvantages of Self Employment:

- Work hours of self-employed may get longer with inconsistent income.
- Relationship between self-employed and the clients plays a big role in the in the business. They can make or break your business.
- Even if your business is small but you will end up paying more tax then that of a regular employee. It's because, you will have to pay both the employer and employee tax and extra local business/mercantile taxes (some in the form of licenses) in addition to regular income tax.
- Self-employed don't get paid leaves like others who are working under someone. You will have to work hard in the starting of the business and sacrifice all your vacations and leaves.
- Employers usually pay for the health insurance of their employees but,

when you are self-employed, you will have to pay for your own health insurance.

- No one knows your business at the start and you will need some really hard work to build up your business reputation.
- Self-employed have more responsibility than working under other, as here you make your business plans and strategies. So none other than you will be responsible for your success and failure.
- At the end of your hard work, still you are not sure to whether your business module will work. In fact you may also go in for loss at times. On the other hand, you are sure to get your salary if you are working under other.

Conclusion:

Self-employment is a good choice for the people who can withstand risk and stress and are determined to achieve what they want to achieve, no matter what comes in the way. But at the same time, self-employment demands good entrepreneurial skills. Simply jumping into it without having the basic skills and knowledge of its advantages and disadvantages won't help you to become successfully self-employed.